

DARIO CEBIC

ANALYSE

Claude Debussy - *Ausgewählte Werke für Klavier I*

„La puerta del Vino”

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The work "La puerta del Vino" is characterized by Andalusian folk music, the PhrygianArabic mode (which influences partly the melody) and Habanera rhythm.

Fig. 1: Phrygian - Arabic mode

In the work, piano is actually thought of as a „great guitar“. The suggestion notes are usually improvised by the guitarists. Snapping suggestions with both hands (in the countermovement) suggest the beating of the bottom of the guitar with the knuckle. In the „La puerta del Vino“ moves above the ostinato bass a melodic upper voice, which is partly expatriated, partly amplified by fifths or parallel chords and is characteristic in the change of duols and triplets.

The Eastin Habanera rhythm can be found in two forms:

- on the notes "of - as" (bars 1 - 41, bar 66 until the end)
- on the notes "b - f" (bars 44 - 56).

Suggestions as to the origin of musical thought the préludes show that Debussy had very different reasons for writing the pieces. Debussy was inspired in this case ("La puerta del Vino") by one of the doors of the city of Alhambra de Granada. The Préludes are not a musical picture book, but sounding processes that have their own laws and follow them. Thus, with distant sounds that transcend the frame of thought, they give listeners the chance to discover a new and diverse palette of colors and their interpretations.

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Form (Shape): A - B - A1

- A part: measure 1 - measure 41

- B-Part: measure 42 - measure 66
- A1-Part: measure 66 until the end

The work begins with the introduction (bars 1-4), in which the initially eerie rhythm in the low pitch leads to an eruption in the higher register, but then breaks off with a seventh chord Des7 (bars 4-5).

Fig. 2: Introduction of „La puerta del Vino“, Habanera rhythm

The melody moves to the sound of the Phrygian-Arabic mode on E, and creates, together with the sound of the ostinato bass, an excessive nonenakkord on Des (Des 9 # / 7). The tone H rises boldly and cheerfully upwards C, becomes D and E and denies all feelings of bondage. The melody lives only for itself, and only late, more on chance or yield than on purpose, does it flow back into a tonal solution to Des.

Fig. 3: bars 5-20, bitonal staining - Phrygian/ Arabic mode with Excessive second

The piece is noted in D flat major, but we often find other scales as well. At the beginning of the work we find the five notes which, if possible, set the overlap with the Phrygian-Arabic mode to E:

Fig. 4: Humiliation of the II, III and VI stages

Instead of continuing this powerful sound, the piano presents an oscillating melody after bar 4. The characteristic Habanera rhythm for this work, which consists, as if unleashed, of several upward leaps, places high demands on the virtuosity of a pianist. In the lyrical middle section the composer presents a wistful melos with the harmonic and rhythmic tension (sechstoleseptolle) in

the right hand. The Sechstole and Septole are also a kind of ornamentation of Andalusian folk music. This vocally influenced part puts the listener in a melancholy world of sound, but ends up in picking up the modulated theme, before ending with an extended sixthgrade septole passage. In this work, the main note are decorated with many ornaments. From bar 6 it is clear to see that in the Habanere rhythm is a d-major to see, whereby he brings a tone H to composer in time 9.

Fig. 5: melody line; Phrygian / Arabic mode

In bars 17-20 we find „melodic cadence“, which led to a chromatic variant of a thematic fragment. In bar 21 the composer anticipates the second idea.

After the repetition of the chromatic cadence, the second idea begins on bar 25 (Rubato), which moves past the tones of the Phrygian mode on E. Here the composer has a threefold overlap of the whole-tone chord in the RH, Pentatonic chord in LH, and the ostinato bass. Again, Debussy uses the same organic typesetting techniques to complement the specifically Iberian-folkloristic color. In bars 33-34 we have a change of major chromatic periods with diatonic thirds in c. This is followed by an eight-bar transition with a gentle melody line. In bar 33, an interval - None is added to a chord. So we have a quasi-dominant seventh chord with None. The rhythmic and melodic elements are repeated.

In the course of the performance, the motif becomes more and more important and ultimately, in conjunction with the triplets, presents a modified form of the theme head. As a result, there is

once again the throbbing eighth note movement, which is here more rhythmically rhythimized by the rhythmic variety. After the quasirecapitulation follows a prolonged version of the melodic transition, the figure appears this time in the reduced form. In bars 35-41 there are sequences of parallel quartet chords over bitonal ostinato Habanerabass, this time the Quint Des-As, first in strict variations (bars 38-41). Therefore, the tonality remains unstable and consolidates only by harmonic congruence between bass and solo in D major final chord.

Fig. 6: Bars 35 - 41 of „La Puerta del vino“

In the B-part (bars 42 - 66) Debussy has a kind of implementation where different meaningful elements are developed. The composer himself has labeled each fragment with a special expression:

- Bar 44 and ff (passionement) fragment from the final idea (bars 35 and ff)
- Bar 50 (ironique) from Habanera rhythm
- Bar 52 from the melodic cadence (bar 17)
- measure 55 (gracieux) again from habanera rhythm.

Then the fragments become even shorter:

- Bar 57 Final idea
- Bar 58 Habanera Rhythmus
- Bar 59 melodic cadence.

The whole B-part moves polarized on the parallel sound (B) and is marked by sharp harmonic conflicts. The B-part starts with quasi 2 introductory bars / a kind of performance (au mouvt - german: beweglich) which lead to the new part (passionément - german: passionate). In these 2 bars we find a dramatic - dynamic part, which leads to an increase of forte "f" to a fortissimo "ff". Only in the bar 44 - measure 49 are again the full chords in their usual function, which then goes back in the clock 52 and clock 59 in the parallel movement. This part also has a bitonal coloring.

In the B section, the composer creates a figuration with chromaticism, which is again used in the following section. Thus we find in the bar 52 chromaticism in the left hand (c - h - be - a) and in bar 59 chromatic in the right hand (es - d - des - c). In the B section, after a kind of performance, the work in B major is changed. The piano still insists on the rhythm, but renounces in the bass on the pulsating figures in favor of calming, lying chords and the sound Des is called Ton Ces. Subsequently, the piano solos the Tyrolean elements of the theme head, often using it as a motif in the casual execution.

Fig. 7: bar 44-47, bitonal staining

In bars 62-65 we find a pedal chord on the dominant, but in the right hand we find a repetition of the VIb with ueb, 5e - V7 also ueb.5e (whole tone chords). So, in this part we also find so-called „gliding chords“. The term „gliding chords“ is used when in chord progression half of the notes remain the same notes. It is actually a transition part which led to the A1 part. The beginning of the reprise moves within a rich harmony, the tonic chord contains not only the seventh and the overpowering ninth as in the beginning, but also the excessive undeclines.

So also the continuation of the melody is reinforced by parallelism. In bar 66 begins A1 - part vobei in the right hand we find tone "g" over 4 bars. Compared to the A-part, the tone "g" for a small sixth after As contrast to the B-part, the A1 part is shortbarreled and rustic. Right at the beginning, the piano with an eighth-note movement in the introduction introduces the stocky character.

The piano part takes over the rhythm in the bass and also plays repetitive dramatic figures in the treble. The „La Puerta del Vino“ does not dissolve in a normal final triad of Des, but in a triad with added Non, which gives the octave only the octave stimulus. The C major melody (bars 5-20 and 66-78) gets bitonal coloring from the D-flat bass.

From bar 70-74 an ostinato des-as is set against the tritone f-h. To the Habanera Quint - Movement organ on this - as from the cadence of „La puerta ...“ from bar 70 pure C sounds emerge. After the cadenza (bars 75-83) we find, as Coda, a shortened reprise of the Second Idea. To the beat of 83-85 we again find the pentatonic, which appears in the same rhythmic figuration as a „memory motif“.

Debussy has characterized with this coda with new harmonic tone color. The melodic line moves on an octatonic fragment (83 - 85: g-fis-e-es abwärts), while the overlap of whole-tone and pentatonic chords is preserved, but begins in a still foreign (lontain = clay reservoir) (the harmony in bar 83 is new: in bar 84 Debussy has repeated the sound of bars 21 and 25). Finally, (bar 85) this chord progression dissolves in a gentle tonic-nonenaccord.